
Physical Exercise and Socio-Emotional Skills as Predictors to Academic Productivity among College Students

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Abstract:

The sudden shift of teaching modality from traditional face to face to online instruction caused by Covid-19 pandemic had caused problems in the teaching-learning process. This quantitative study aimed to determine the degree of association of physical exercise, socio-emotional skills and their academic productivity. The linear regression analysis to describe the possible existing relationship between identified variables as well as determining the direction and magnitude of such relationship. It was discovered that the overall level of students' physical exercise, socio-emotional skills and academic activity is high. This indicated that the three variables are much observed by the college students. After the thorough investigation, the null hypothesis ($p < 0.05$) was rejected. This study delineated that physical exercise and socio-emotional skills predicted student academic productivity. The study accentuated that physical exercise and socio-emotional skills are crucial to boosting students' academic productivity.

Keywords: Physical Education, physical exercise, socio-emotional skills, academic productivity, Philippines

1. Introduction

Previous studies revealed that students and teachers greatly affected by the abrupt change of teaching modality from traditional instruction to online teaching modality due to the Covid-19 pandemic. It was also discovered that teaching of practical content got a poor rating. In comparison to past years, the proportion of students who are extremely dissatisfied with their current condition has increased by one percentage point, while the number of students who are extremely satisfied has nearly halved. In 2018, 18 percent of students stated they were extremely dissatisfied with their outputs with the current circumstances, compared to 34 and 31 percent in 2018 and 2016, respectively (Pfister, et al., 2021). The study conducted in Germany also revealed that the problem of academic productivity also caused by procrastination and mediocrity among the students in online courses and the time pressure and burnout brought by this modality which, in turn, academic health-related loss and academic productivity in the long run (Mirzoyan and Mikaelyan, 2022).

In the Philippine context, remote learning has the potential to increase inequalities and create obstacles to online learning. There are thirty-two percent (32%) and twenty-two percent (22%) of 3,670 Filipino students, have difficulty adjusting to new learning techniques and do not have dependable internet connection, respectively. For some, purchasing a learning gadget that allows them to effortlessly tune in to online classes and turn in assignments in the online system may be tough. Despite attempts to make education more accessible to all, Filipino university students who choose remote education face several challenges (Baticulon, 2020).

The productivity in education is significant on many levels. In the study of Karadag (2018) revealed that instructors and their productive actions and operations are one of the most significant

things to promote during the transition process of colleges and universities into third generation educational institutions. It should be emphasized that universities must improve their missions to conduct scientific research, which is one of their purposes of establishment, in order to gain competitive advantage in the modern world, where students and instructors' mobility, innovation, technology, and information-based economic policies are all predominant. In the 21st century when innovation and skills are considered as the key driving factors, colleges and universities that are the center of search and development operations, as well as instructors who are the essential aspects of universities, could not withstand the worldwide trend for long against global tendency.

The benefits of consistent physical activity have been demonstrated to have a favorable impact on a variety of metabolic activities, including such as heart rate, platelet function and etc., as well as being linked to a reduction in chronic non-contagious disorders respiratory illnesses. However, in recent decades, increases in brain structures have been connected to improvements in cognitive abilities such as attention, memory, planning, inhibition, and so on. This final circumstance has allowed researchers to establish a link between physical activity and academic productivity (Maureira, and Diaz, 2018).

On the other hand, Alzahrani, Alharbi, and Alodwani (2019) emphasized that social and emotional skills are essential in building a productive learner especially in today' educational system. The reinforcement of the socio-emotional dimension in the educational environment aids students in achieving their learning objectives. With this, teachers must focus on helping students to develop healthy social and emotional skills. The development of students' social and emotional competency has a direct impact on their motivation to learn and consequently on their current and future academic success. Furthermore, additional social and emotional support for students is required to ensure academic productivity and high-test score results. They are more likely to be ready for school-related activities and to perform well in their academic tasks when they feel joyful, comfortable, loved, understood, and listened to than if they do not feel these qualities.

The researcher did not find studies that examine physical exercise and socio-emotional skills as Predictors to Academic Productivity among college students. Most of the previous studies only include either physical exercise or socio-emotional skills as its independent variable separately. Many studies have directly focus on the effects of the aforementioned factors on the academic success of the students in general, not on the level productivity. This study focuses on determining students' physical exercise and socio-emotional skills and identifying which among students' physical exercise and socio-emotional skills most significantly predicts students' academic productivity. The result of this study may be helpful in refining and promoting student academic productivity as it is believed important in academic success. With that, instructors and school administrators may utilize this as their basis in formulating innovative pedagogical approaches to improve student's learning experiences. Considering the limited researches that scrutinize the current trends of instruction, especially in promoting academic productivity, this study might be helpful in future studies. Thus, the urgency to conduct the study. This study may benefit the students to enhance their productivity level and will also help them improve their learning mechanisms. It is also beneficial to the college instructors and administrators to have the basis for taking steps on addressing the issue of academic productivity among college students and to establish feasible intervention.

2. Literature Review

The reviewed literature offers in-depth insights into the key variables of the study: physical exercise, socio-emotional skills, and academic productivity.

In their study, Sullivan, Johnson, and Owens (2017) highlighted that students' growth and academic success are significantly influenced by their level of physical exercise. Conner (2019) also argued that incorporating physical activities into the classroom setting promotes the introduction of physical education. Physical activity has been shown to improve the study habits of many college students. Previous research recommended that instructors should increase the level of physical exercise among students, warning that continued cuts to sports activities by school administrations could have long-term negative effects.

The study of Lobelo et al. (2019) identified physical inactivity as a prevalent major health risk factor associated with a high burden of cardiovascular disease. They emphasized that increasing and maintaining recommended levels of physical exercise reduces metabolic, hemodynamic, functional, body composition, and epigenetic risk factors for noncommunicable chronic diseases. Physical exercise is vital in the prevention and treatment of over 40 diseases, including diabetes mellitus, cancer, cardiovascular disease, obesity, depression, Alzheimer's disease, and arthritis, often playing a role as effective as or even superior to medication therapies.

In his study, Matiba (2015) eloquently highlighted that physical activity contributes to numerous beneficial outcomes, including improved physical and mental health, enhanced social well-being, and better cognitive and academic performance. Individuals who engage in physical activity and participate in team sports are less likely to engage in harmful behaviors, such as substance abuse and unsafe sexual practices, compared to non-participants. Conversely, a consistently sedentary lifestyle is associated with lower educational achievement, poor self-perceived health, and an overall less healthy lifestyle.

However, Vaara et al. (2019) found that there is a significant gap in awareness regarding recommended physical exercise guidelines, with many individuals lacking knowledge about these recommendations, particularly those related to aerobic exercise. This lack of familiarity suggests that current efforts to communicate and implement exercise guidelines are insufficient. To address this issue, there is a pressing need for more robust and proactive strategies to raise awareness and educate the public about the importance and specifics of physical exercise. Enhancing the dissemination of these guidelines could help improve overall public health and encourage more individuals to adopt healthier lifestyles.

It is noteworthy that in the study of Shujaat (2018) noted that Pakistani students have a positive attitude toward physical activities and enjoy participating in them to improve their health. They recognize the benefits of engaging in sports and physical activities, with cricket being the most popular sport among them. In contrast, Dunton, Do, and Wang (2020) found that the restrictions on mobility and school engagement, along with the cancellation of sporting events and other activities in 2020, had a significant impact on students' lives.

As heighted by Ennis (2017) emphasized that many students, teens, and young adults are still missing out on the benefits of leading an active lifestyle. To enhance programming and achieve physical activity goals, teachers and program directors need to focus on strategies that effectively increase students' physical activity outside of class. Transformative physical education (PE) provides physical activity content in a supportive and motivating environment, with the potential to profoundly impact students' lives. By incorporating sports, physical exercise, dance,

and adventure activities, teachers can maintain their commitment to effective, standards-based instruction while preparing students for a lifetime of physical activity and personal and social development.

The study by Guo and Zhang (2022) emphasizes that as awareness of mental health issues increases, people are reassessing the role of physical activity in improving overall well-being, leading to a more comprehensive examination of its benefits. This shift in perspective emphasizes that physical activity is not only beneficial for physical health but also crucial for mental and emotional stability. Given that teenagers represent the future of our society, it is essential that their education addresses their mental and emotional development in addition to their physical health. By integrating these elements, educational programs can better support holistic growth and prepare adolescents for future challenges.

It was argued by Dunton et al. (2020) argued that social interaction plays a crucial role in physical education and health. Through interacting with their peers, students develop mobility and cooperative skills. However, during the Covid-19 pandemic in 2020, students were less physically active due to the inability to participate in school-based physical activities. The need for social distancing to prevent the spread of Covid-19 limited their engagement in physical exercise. As a result, most students and teachers turned to social media platforms for communication and instruction. As recommended by Göktaş (2015) recommended that teachers should be mindful of their students' perceptions of Facebook as an interactive environment, given that interaction is a vital component of sports activities. Understanding these perceptions could help address issues related to student-teacher interactions. Moreover, while Facebook can offer a platform for interaction, it also presents challenges for students in terms of face-to-face engagement. However, students who participate in sports are less likely to exhibit passive behaviors, highlighting the importance of active participation in physical activities.

It was discussed by Villar et al. (2021) emphasized the importance of promoting socio-emotional competency through targeted and effective educational initiatives. By enhancing social skills and emotion regulation, schools can foster democratic coexistence and improve conflict resolution. This approach has significant practical implications for achieving the well-being and high-quality education that is sought in the field of education.

The study of Ibach's (2017) study highlighted the essential role of self-awareness as a life skill, stressing that higher education professionals must implement strategies to cultivate this skill on college campuses. Such initiatives could take various forms, including programs in residence halls or mental health promotion efforts. The need to promote self-awareness among college students is crucial and should be a priority for those working in higher education. Additionally, it was claimed by Garrecht et al. (2018) further argued that responsible decision-making is a vital skill, not only in business but also in everyday life. Decision-making is a key component of problem-solving and is especially important in management and leadership roles. Colleges should, therefore, focus on nurturing this kind of leadership among their students.

It was pointed out in the study of Firmante (2019) highlighted the importance of relationship management skills in students' daily lives, extending through their college years and beyond. The study found that social and emotional learning competencies positively impact students' academic performance, promote physical health, enhance citizenship, and are vital for future careers and lifelong learning. Given that relationship management can contribute to

developing an evidence-based curriculum, exploring its role in career planning is particularly significant. In addition, Jayousi (2016) emphasized that modern telecommunication technologies have transformed how individuals socialize, shortening distances, strengthening social ties, and facilitating collective projects and education. This adaptation to new communication methods underscores the evolving nature of relationship management in both personal and professional contexts.

More so, Matitaputty et al. (2018) eloquently argued that social awareness education is essential for students to develop their critical thinking abilities and to foster social change. By gaining a deeper understanding of the behaviors of their peers, both academically and non-academically, students cultivate a greater appreciation for life over time. Additionally, they value the opportunity to engage personally with underprivileged and homeless children, which enriches their perspective.

Furthermore, Muluk et al. (2021) emphasized that students have significant control over altering or adapting their immediate physical and social environments. They learn when to work independently or collaboratively, when to seek support from others, and when to adjust to or modify their surroundings. Success in academic coursework is closely tied to students' abilities in time management and activity organization. The development of self-management skills has a profound impact on both their academic and social lives, contributing to their overall success.

The study of Alyami, et al., (2021) discovered that students produce better outputs and achieve the learning objectives if they are able to manage their time and behavior at school. It would be more beneficial for their academic productivity if they have better preplan their studies. The quality of teacher-student interactions in the classroom is a critical determinant of overall student involvement and achievement. By fostering positive, respectful, and engaging interactions, teachers can cultivate a supportive learning environment that empowers students to thrive academically and personally.

The K to 12 Curriculum Guide (2012) outlines that it is the duty of tertiary universities and colleges to provide students with access to advanced and practical technology, ensuring that their educational experience is aligned with contemporary technological standards. Similarly, Abdullah and Muait (2019) underscore the importance of technological skills in today's educational environment, highlighting that proficiency in these skills is critical for students' success. The rapid advancement of information and communication technology has introduced a variety of tools and resources that are essential for effective learning and are available to a broad audience. These technological resources facilitate enhanced learning opportunities, making it crucial for educational institutions to integrate them into their curricula to better prepare students for the demands of the modern world.

Additionally, Ramli and Zainv (2019) noted that newly established educational institutions often struggle to provide adequate learning facilities, which can significantly affect students' academic performance. Classrooms play a critical role in shaping students' aspirations and providing the skills and knowledge necessary to achieve their future goals. Thus, the quality of learning environments directly influences students' academic productivity and their ability to realize their potential.

The study by Nonis and Hudson (2022) emphasized that study habits are fundamental practices that enable learners to absorb and process information effectively, thereby enhancing

their academic productivity. Their research also highlighted that poor study habits can significantly impact academic performance.

Moreover, Carter (2019) identified a range of educational distractions affecting students, including dissatisfaction, indifference, and disillusionment, which contribute to widening the gap in academic success. Schools are expected to provide learning opportunities that facilitate students' integration into society. However, Gesualdi's (2019) phenomenological study revealed that active student participation is a strong predictor of academic success.

Additionally, Sumaira et al. (2018) demonstrated that physical exercise has a profound effect on academic performance, highlighting its critical role in education. This finding underscores the necessity of integrating physical activity into school curricula, as it can significantly contribute to students' overall success. Physical exercise is known to alleviate mental health issues such as depression, stress, and anxiety, which can otherwise hinder academic achievement. Furthermore, engaging in regular physical activity helps to boost self-esteem, creating a positive feedback loop that enhances both students' mental well-being and their academic performance. Therefore, educational institutions should prioritize physical exercise as a key component of their programs to support students' holistic development.

The study of Alzahrani et al. (2019) emphasized that the home is the primary environment where students begin their development and learning, followed by the classroom. The interactions between teachers and students can influence both learning outcomes and students' personalities. Positive interactions and a supportive school environment led to greater productivity in both academic and social aspects. Additionally, holistic development contributes to students' long-term success, particularly in their academic pursuits.

3. Material and Methods

This section presents the research design, research locale, population and sample, research instruments, procedures for data collection and statistical tool to be used in the study.

Research Design

This is a quantitative study, specifically a causal-comparative research design which is also known as *ex post facto* research design. This is a research design that seeks to find relationships between independent and dependent variables after an action or event has already occurred which means that the purpose of research is to investigate whether the independent variables affected the dependent variable (outcome) by comparing two or more groups or samples (Salkind, 2010). The study emphasized the aim of the researcher which is to determine the ability of the independent variables (physical exercise and socio-emotional skills) to affect the academic productivity among the college students. In this sense, a causal-comparative research design was needed in this study.

This study also employed linear regression analysis to describe the possible existing relationship between identified variables as well as determining the direction and magnitude of such relationship, if there is. Linear regression analysis was used in this research since it was considered to be useful in determining the strength of the relationship between the two independent variables and a dependent variable. The quantitative method was appropriate for gathering the data for the target respondents to answer the questions reflected in the survey questionnaire.

Research Locale

This study applied the cluster sampling technique in selecting the respondents of the study. Out of all tertiary education institutions in Davao de Oro, only two (2) higher educational institutions were chosen to represent the entire population. The subjects of the study were the teacher education students, who were specialized in Secondary Education and Elementary Education enrolled in the year 2021-2022. The respondents can withdraw anytime if they are threatened in the conduct of the study.

The researcher used the Slovin's formula: $(n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2})$. Where "n" pertains to the sample size, "N" refers population size and "e" denotes the margin of error) to determine the number of samples.

Table 1. The Distribution of Respondents.

Population of Teacher Education Students	Respondents
Campus A = 508	220
Campus B = 272	160
Total = 770	380

Research Instrument

The researcher used an adapted questionnaire for the independent and dependent variables to suit the context of the study. The gathered data from the research were linked to the literature to aid the construction of the survey questionnaire which were validated by the panel of internal and external validators. The respondents were given a questionnaire that contains the respondent's the three sets of questionnaires for the independent and dependent variables.

The first set of questionnaires was dealing with the engagement of students in physical exercise. The survey questionnaire in the first independent variable was taken from the adapted questionnaire of Kadariya and Aro, (2018) entitled "Barriers and facilitators to physical activity among urban residents with diabetes in Nepal". The aforementioned survey questionnaire contains 29 statements that were consist of the following domains; life enhancement (8 items), physical performance (8 items), psychological outlook (6 items), social interaction (4 items), and preventive health (3 items) which were rated using the 7-points Likert scale.

The original survey questionnaire was modified to accommodate the school setting. To get a deeper interpretation from the respondents, the initial items were simplified or paraphrased, and were validated by the expert panel. Reliability was also be put to the test. For each item, the participants were requested to rate the physical exercise of student using the 5-points Likert scale anchored at (5) Very High, (4) High, (3) Moderate, (2) Low, and (1) Very Low.

The second set of survey questionnaire was dealing with student motivation. The survey questionnaire in the second independent variable will be taken from the third part of questionnaire in the study of Zhou, and Ee (2012). The original form of questionnaire contains 25 items which was consists of five domains; self-awareness (5 items), social awareness (5 items), self-management (5 items), relationship management (5 items), and responsible decision making (5 items).

The original survey questionnaire was modified to contextualize the school setting. The original items were simplified or paraphrased to gain better understanding from the respondents. The questionnaire was validated by the panel of experts. It also undergone the test of validity and reliability. For each item, the participants were requested to rate the physical exercise of students using the 5-points Likert scale anchored at (5) Very High, (4) High, (3) Moderate, (2) Low, and (1) Very Low.

The third set of survey questionnaire embarks with academic productivity among college students. The survey questionnaire in the dependent variable was taken after the adapted questionnaire of Pfister, Mika, Pavic, and Nguyen (2021) in their study entitled “Student productivity in the transition to online lectures”. Moreover, the following benchmarks were established for the effective educational practices; learning facilities (3 items), technology use (3 items), interaction process (4 items), student participation (5 items), study time (3 items).

The initial sample questionnaire was modified to contextualize the school setting. To ensure that the respondents understood the original questionnaire, it was paraphrased and the validity and durability were also tested. For each item, the participants were requested to rate the student engagement using the 5-points Likert scale anchored at (5) Very High, (4) High, (3) Moderate, (2) Low, and (1) Very Low. It should be noted that the instruments used in this study were validated by the panel of experts.

Statistical Analysis

This research also employed statistical tools in processing the answers to the questions at 5% level of significance. The responses obtained from all the items in the questionnaires were tallied, tabulated and interpreted. The **Mean** was used to determine the levels of engagement in physical exercise, socio-emotional skills and the academic productivity among teacher education students across the selected institutions in Davao de Oro. The **Pearson-r** was used to determine the significance on the relationship between factor’s physical exercise, socio-emotional skills and the academic productivity among teacher education students across the selected institutions in Davao de Oro. The **Linear Regression Analysis** was employed to determine which among the students’ physical exercise, socio-emotional skills significantly predict the academic productivity among teacher education students across the selected institutions in Davao de Oro.

4. Results and Discussion

In this section, the results, analysis, and intervention derived from the conducted study are presented. The information was presented in both tabular and textual formats. At a significance threshold of 0.05, all inferential results were evaluated and interpreted. Tables and their interpretation were organized chronologically under the following headings: level of students’ physical exercise, socio-emotional skills and academic productivity among college students, the significance of the relationship between physical exercise, socio-emotional skills and academic productivity, and regression analysis on physical exercise and socio-emotional skills as predictors to students’ academic productivity.

Level of Students’ Physical Exercise

The table 1 shows the level of physical exercise in terms of the indicators— life enhancement, physical performance, psychological outlook, social interaction, and preventive health is presented in the table below. The overall level of students’ physical exercise is high. This indicates that the physical exercise is observed by the college students. This result is connected to the study of Sullivan, Johnson, and Owens (2017) that students’ growth and academic success depend greatly on their level of physical exercise. Additionally, Conner (2019), claimed that physical activities encourage the introduction of physical education in the classroom. Many college students’ studying habits have been improved by physical activity. Previous studies gave recommendations for instructors to enhance the degree of physical exercise among students should be increased. They may be affected in the long term if the school administration continues to cut off the sports activities.

Table 1. Level of Student’s Physical Exercise

**PHYSICAL EXERCISE AND SOCIO-EMOTIONAL SKILLS AS PREDICTORS TO ACADEMIC
PRODUCTIVITY AMONG COLLEGE STUDENTS**

Indicators	Mean	SD	Descriptive Equivalent
Life Enhancement	4.06	0.797	High
Physical Performance	4.08	0.836	high
Psychological Outlook	3.89	0.837	High
Social Interaction	3.38	0.889	Moderate
Preventive Health	4.15	0.832	High
Overall	3.91	0.671	High

Among the five indicators, preventive health got the highest mean of 4.15 which is described as high. This relates to the study of Lobelo et al. (2019) that physical inactivity is one of the most common main health risk factors and is linked to a high burden of cardiovascular disease. Reducing metabolic, hemodynamic, functional, body composition, and epigenetic risk factors for noncommunicable chronic illnesses is achieved by increasing and maintaining recommended amounts of physical exercise. Physical activity is crucial in the prevention and treatment of over 40 illnesses, including diabetes mellitus, cancer, cardiovascular disease, obesity, depression, Alzheimer's disease, and arthritis. Physical exercise plays a substantial role that is frequently equivalent to or superior than medication therapies.

In his study, it was eloquently stated by Matiba (2015) that physical activity is acknowledged as a factor in a number of advantageous outcomes for individual's physical and mental health, social wellbeing, and cognitive and academic performances. People who are physically active and take part in team sports are less likely than non-participants to engage in harmful behavior including substance misuse and unsafe sexual practices. Consistently living a sedentary lifestyle was linked to low educational outcomes, poor self-perceived health, and a less healthy lifestyle.

However, it was revealed by Vaara, et al. (2019) that there are only few people who are aware about the recommended physical exercise. Also, only a few researches have examined understanding of and knowledge with recommendations for aerobic type of physical activity. Therefore, more aggressive efforts are required to promote the guidelines for physical exercise.

The result also revealed that physical performance was much observed by the college students. It is noteworthy that in the study of Shujaat (2018), the Pakistani students have a positive attitude toward physical activities and like participating in them to enhance their health. They understand the advantages of participation in sports and physical activities. Cricket is the most popular sport among Pakistani students (Shujaat, 2018). Contrarywise this, a study conducted by Dunton, Do, and Wang (2020) the lives of students have been significantly impacted by the limitations on mobility and engage effectively in schools, as well as the cancellation of sporting events and other activities in the year 2020.

Meanwhile, the physical exercise influenced by physical enhancement, also turned to be much observed by the college students. As heightened by Ennis (2017) that many of the advantages of leading an active lifestyle are still elusive for some students, teens, and young adults. Teachers and program directors need to concentrate programmatic emphasis on techniques to really raise students' out-of-class physical activity behavior if they want to improve programming and performance to fulfill physical activity goals. Transformative PE offers physical activity material in a supportive and inspiring setting that has the power to transform students' lives. Teachers can uphold their commitment to successful standards-based teaching while educating students for a lifetime of physical activity by using sport, physical exercise, dance, and adventure activities as the means to an end for personal and social growth.

PHYSICAL EXERCISE AND SOCIO-EMOTIONAL SKILLS AS PREDICTORS TO ACADEMIC PRODUCTIVITY AMONG COLLEGE STUDENTS

Accordingly, psychological outlook was also found to be much observed by the college students. The result of the study of Guo and Zhang (2022) implied that people's deep awareness of the idea of mental health has led them to develop a new view of the purpose of physical activity and attempt to conduct a thorough investigation into this purpose. Teenagers are seen to be the driving force behind our society's future growth, thus when educating them, we should focus on developing their mental and emotional faculties as well as their physical faculties.

Finally, social interaction, were discovered to be observed by the college students. It was argued by Dunton, et al (2020) that social interaction is a key component in the field of physical education and health. Students gain mobility and the capacity for cooperation via interaction with one another. However, Dunton, et al (2020) revealed that students were less physically active in the year 2020 during the Covid-19 pandemic since they could not really participate in school-based physical activities. They did not participate in much physical exercise, despite the fact that Covid-19 must be kept from spreading through social isolation. Most of the students and teachers used social media platform as the tool for communication and instruction. As recommended by Göktaş (2015), teachers must be aware of their students' opinions of Facebook as an interactive environment because interaction is an essential component of sports activities. That could raise awareness of issues involving interactions between students and instructors. Furthermore, it is clear that Facebook provides students with difficulties in face-to-face engagement with an environment for interaction. Students that participate in sports will be less likely to engage in passive behaviors as a result

Level of Students’ Socio-emotional Skills

The level of Students’ socio-emotional skills in terms of the indicators— self-awareness, social awareness, self-management, relationship management, and responsible decision making is presented in the table below. The overall level of students’ socio-emotional skills is high. This indicates that the level of socio-emotional skills among college students is much observed. The result subscribes to the of Villar, et al., (2021) that socio-emotional competency should be encouraged through dedicated and successful educational initiatives. In order to promote dispute resolution and foster democratic coexistence in schools, it is possible to strengthen social skills and emotion control. This has significant and practical ramifications for delivering the wellbeing and high-quality education we strive for in the field of education.

Table 2. Level of Students’ Socio-emotional Skills

Indicators	Mean	SD	Descriptive Equivalent
Self-awareness	4.18	0.801	High
Social Awareness	3.94	0.841	High
Self-management	3.86	0.837	High
Relationship Management	4.02	0.813	High
Responsible Decision Making	4.18	0.803	High
Overall	4.04	0.704	High

In this variable, both self-awareness and responsible decision making were found to be much observed by the college students. This is parallel to the study of Ibach (2017) that the current studies showed self-awareness is a life skill that is essential. The requirement for self-awareness must be implemented on college campuses by higher education professionals. This implementation could take a varied form, such as in the resident halls or through mental health promotion. The necessity to encourage self-awareness among college students, however, must be acknowledged by those working in higher education. Additionally, it was claimed by Garrecht et al., (2018) that

responsible making decisions is a crucial skill for both business and daily life. Making decisions is a crucial part of problem-solving and is crucial for management and leadership roles. We should anticipate this kind of leadership from our college students.

Additionally, the indicator relationship management, was found to be much observed by the college students. It conforms to the study of Firmante (2019) which pointed out that the value of relationship management abilities in students' daily life up till they graduate from college. It has been discovered that social and emotional learning competency has favorable impacts on students' academic performance, promotes physical health, improves citizenship, and is crucial to future careers and lifetime learning. Given that relationship management might aid in creating an evidence-based curriculum for students, it is significant to investigate its function in career planning. Jayousi (2016) added that individuals have adapted the modern telecommunication technologies to socialize with other people for it shortened distances, consolidated social ties, and allowed individuals to use it for collective projects and education.

Meanwhile, social awareness was found to be much observed by the college students. In relation to the study of Matitaputty, et al., (2018), students need social awareness education to develop their critical thinking abilities and to promote social change. They can comprehend the actions of the kids they are with both academically and non-academically. As a result, their appreciation of life grows as time passes. In addition, they are appreciative of the chance to speak with the underprivileged and homeless kids in person.

Finally, the study revealed that self-management got the lowest mean score but much observed by the college students. This result is similar to the study of Muluk, et al., (2021) that students have complete control over changing or modifying their immediate physical and social surroundings. They understand when it is necessary to work alone or in a group, when it is appropriate to ask for support from others, and when it is appropriate to adapt to and modify their surroundings. The success of students in completing their coursework depends, among other things, on their capacity for time management and activity organization. Impacts of students' self-management abilities on their academic and social lives.

Level of Academic Productivity

The level of students’ academic productivity in terms of the indicators— learning facilities, technology use, interaction process, student participation, and study time is presented in the table below. The overall level of students’ academic productivity is high. This implied that the level of academic productivity among college students is much observed by the college students. This is parallel to the study of Alyami, et al., (2021) that students produce better outputs and achieve the learning objectives if they are able to manage their time and behavior at school. It would be more beneficial for their academic productivity if they have better preplan their studies. The quality of teacher-student interactions in the classroom is a critical determinant of overall student involvement and achievement. By fostering positive, respectful, and engaging interactions, teachers can cultivate a supportive learning environment that empowers students to thrive academically and personally.

Table 3. Level of Academic Productivity

Indicators	Mean	SD	Descriptive Equivalent
Learning Facilities	3.72	0.882	High

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Technology Use	3.76	0.888	High
Interaction Process	4.12	0.805	High
Student Participation	3.37	0.794	Moderate
Study Time	3.68	0.881	High
Overall	3.73	0.671	High

Among all domains of academic productivity, interaction process got the highest mean of 4.12 which is described as high. This finding is similar to the study of Kovshar et al (2018) that the interaction process is indeed highly observable across various domains of academic productivity, particularly in collaborative learning environments. He also highlights the significance of online group cognition, emphasizing that co-presence and intersubjective shared understanding are crucial for fostering academically productive discourse in computer-supported collaborative learning settings. This suggests that the dynamics of interaction can be effectively monitored and analyzed, providing insights into the collaborative knowledge-building process.

The interaction process is indeed highly observable across various domains of academic productivity, particularly in collaborative learning environments. He also highlights the significance of online group cognition, emphasizing that co-presence and intersubjective shared understanding are crucial for fostering academically productive discourse in computer-supported collaborative learning settings. This suggests that the dynamics of interaction can be effectively monitored and analyzed, providing insights into the collaborative knowledge-building process (Kovshar, et al, 2018).

The student productivity influenced by technology use, was found to be observed by the college students. According to learners K to 12 Curriculum Guide (2012) it is the prerogative of the tertiary universities and colleges to provide advanced and useful technology for students. Furthermore, Abdullah and Muait (2019) asserted that technological skill is one of the several skills to be developed by the Modern technology is the development of information and communication technology which are available for different consumers especially in the field of learning.

Moreover, student productivity influenced by learning facilities was found to be observed by the college students. This result is connected to the study of Ramli and Zainv (2019) that a newly established educational institutions sometimes fail to provide adequate learning facilities to the learners which cause a significant impact in their academic productivity. The classrooms are said to be the place where the learners develop their aspiration of what they want to become in the future, as well as the skills and knowledge that are essential to achieve that aspiration.

More so, student productivity influenced by study time was also found to be much observed by the college students. The study of Nonis and Hudson (2022) highlighted that study habits are the natural practices which allows the learners receive information through learning. It helps the learners improve their academic productivity. Moreover, it was discussed in their study that poor study habits have significant impact in their academic performance.

Student productivity influenced by student participation got the lowest mean but still found to be observed by the college students. It was revealed by Carter (2019) that students are suffering from a wide spectrum of educational distracters, such as dissatisfaction, indifference, and disillusionment, thereby expanding the success disparity. Schools are supposed to give learning opportunities that help the students to integrate into society. However, the phenomenological study by Gesualdi, (2019) revealed that student participation is a good predictor of academic success.

Association of Students' Physical Exercise and Academic Productivity

Pearson* Correlation is conducted to test the relationship between level of physical activity and academic productivity.

Table 4. Association of Students' Physical Exercise and Academic Productivity

Independent Variable	Dependent Variable	r-value	r-squared	p-value	Decision $\alpha = 0.05$
Life Enhancement		0.613*	0.375769	0.000	Ho is rejected
Physical Performance		0.572*	0.327184	0.000	Ho is rejected
Psychological Outlook	Academic Productivity	0.588*	0.345744	0.000	Ho is rejected
Social Interaction		0.520*	0.2704	0.000	Ho is rejected
Preventive Health		0.527*	0.277729	0.000	Ho is rejected
Overall Physical Exercise		0.647*	0.418609	0.000	Ho is rejected

*correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Life Enhancement. The result shows a **strong positive correlation** between life enhancement and academic productivity at $\rho = 0.613$, which was statistically significant at $p < 0.000$. This means that there is sufficient evidence to conclude that the correlation between life enhancement and academic productivity performance is not zero.

Physical Performance. The result shows a **moderate positive correlation** between physical performance and academic productivity at $\rho = 0.572$, which was statistically significant at $p < 0.000$. This means that there is sufficient evidence to conclude that the correlation between physical performance and academic productivity performance is not zero.

Psychological Outlook. The result shows a **moderate positive correlation** between psychological outlook and academic productivity at $\rho = 0.588$, which was statistically significant at $p < 0.000$. This means that there is sufficient evidence to conclude that the correlation between psychological outlook and academic productivity performance is not zero.

Social Interaction. The result shows a **moderate positive correlation** between social interaction and academic productivity at $\rho = 0.520$, which was statistically significant at $p < 0.000$. This means that there is sufficient evidence to conclude that the correlation between social interaction and academic productivity performance is not zero.

Preventive Health. The result shows a **moderate positive correlation** between preventive health and academic productivity at $\rho = 0.527$, which was statistically significant at $p < 0.000$. This means that there is sufficient evidence to conclude that the correlation between preventive health and academic productivity performance is not zero.

Overall Students' Physical Exercise. The result shows a **strong positive correlation** between students' physical exercise and academic productivity at $\rho = 0.647$, which was statistically significant at $p < 0.000$. This means that there is sufficient evidence to conclude that the correlation between students' physical exercise and academic productivity performance is not zero.

Since all indicators in this variable have a p-value of 0.000, which is obviously less than 0.05 level of significance, this allows the researcher to reject the null hypothesis, which states that

“there is no domain in physical exercise that significantly influences academic productivity”. Thus, all domains in physical exercise influence the academic productivity among college students. The result is supported by the study of Sumaira, et al., (2018), physical exercise had a substantial overall influence on academic performance. As a result, the relevance of physical exercise must be considered while developing an educational institution's curriculum. It attempts to improve students' academic performance by reducing depression, tension, and anxiety and boosting self-esteem (Ariza, et al., 2017).

Association of Socio-emotional Skills and Academic Productivity

Pearson* Correlation is conducted to test the relationship between level of socio-emotional skills and academic productivity.

Self-Awareness. The result shows a **strong positive correlation** between self-awareness and academic productivity at rho = 0.653, which was statistically significant at p < 0.000. This means that there is sufficient evidence to conclude that the correlation between self-awareness and academic productivity performance is not zero.

Table 5. Association of Socio-emotional Skills and Academic Productivity

Independent Variable	Dependent Variable	r-value	r-squared	p-value	Decision α = 0.05
Self-awareness		0.653*	0.426409	0.000	Ho is rejected
Social Awareness		0.588*	0.345744	0.000	Ho is rejected
Self-management		0.648*	0.419904	0.000	Ho is rejected
Relationship Management	Academic Productivity	0.610*	0.3721	0.000	Ho is rejected
Responsible Decision Making		0.633*	0.400689	0.000	Ho is rejected
Overall Socio-emotional Skills		0.728*	0.529984	0.000	Ho is rejected

*correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Social Awareness. The result shows a **moderate positive correlation** between social awareness and academic productivity at rho = 0.588, which was statistically significant at p < 0.000. This means that there is sufficient evidence to conclude that the correlation between social awareness and academic productivity performance is not zero.

Self-Management. The result shows a **strong positive correlation** between self-management and academic productivity at rho = 0.648, which was statistically significant at p < 0.000. This means that there is sufficient evidence to conclude that the correlation between self-management and academic productivity performance is not zero.

Relationship Management. The result shows a **strong positive correlation** between relationship management and academic productivity at rho = 0.610, which was statistically significant at p < 0.000. This means that there is sufficient evidence to conclude that the correlation between relationship management and academic productivity performance is not zero.

Responsible Decision Making. The result shows a **strong positive correlation** between responsible decision making and academic productivity at rho = 0.633, which was statistically significant at p < 0.000. This means that there is sufficient evidence to conclude that the correlation between responsible decision making and academic productivity performance is not zero.

Overall Socio-emotional Skills. The result shows a **very strong positive correlation** between socio-emotional skills and academic productivity at $\rho = 0.728$, which was statistically significant at $p < 0.000$. This means that there is sufficient evidence to conclude that the correlation between socio-emotional skills and academic productivity performance is not zero.

The results revealed that all indicators in this variable have a p-value of 0.000, which is clearly less than the level of significance of 0.05, this allows the researcher to reject the null hypothesis, which states that “there is no domain in socio-emotional skills that significantly influences academic productivity”. Thus, all domains in socio-emotional skills influence the academic productivity among college students. This is in concordance to the study of Alzahrani, et al., (2019) that the first place where students develop and learn is at home; the second is in a classroom. Both the learning results and personalities of students can be impacted by the interactions between instructors and students. They are more productive in both their academic and social lives when there is more optimism in these connections and the school environment. Additionally, healthy growth in every area of development benefits students’ life throughout time, particularly their academic life.

Regression Analysis on How the Domains of Physical Exercise predict Academic Productivity

Using Multiple Linear Regression analysis, the regression model of academic productivity in terms of the domains of student’s physical exercise is:

$$Y = 1.374 + 0.231X_1 + 0.067X_2 + 0.116X_3 + 0.078X_4 + 0.106X_5$$

The results of the Student’s t-test, shown above indicate that only life enhancement and physical performance are significant. These results prove that the estimated regression coefficients of said indicators are significantly different from zero, signifying only life enhancement and physical performance are meaningful additions to the model. Consequently, F-test revealed that the composite hypothesis that all regression coefficients are equal to zero is also highly significant with an F-statistic of 54.920 and a p-value of < 0.000 . Finally, the adjusted R^2 revealed that the model could explain approximately 42% of the variation in the level of academic productivity of the students. This suggests that 42% of the variability in the observed levels of academic productivity of the respondents can be attributed to the domains of physical exercise.

The results of the Student’s t-test, shown above indicate that only life enhancement and physical performance are significant. These results prove that the estimated regression coefficients of said indicators are significantly different from zero, signifying only life enhancement and physical performance are meaningful additions to the model. Consequently, F-test revealed that the composite hypothesis that all regression coefficients are equal to zero is also highly significant with an F-statistic of 54.920 and a p-value of < 0.000 . Finally, the adjusted R^2 revealed that the model could explain approximately 42% of the variation in the level of academic productivity of the students. This suggests that 42% of the variability in the observed levels of academic productivity of the respondents can be attributed to the domains of physical exercise

Table 6. Regression Analysis on How the Domains of Physical Exercise predict Academic Productivity

Model	Unstandardized coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t-value	p-value	Decision
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
(Constant)	1.374	0.150		9.159	0.000	

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Life Enhancement	0.231	0.068	0.274	3.412	0.000	Ho is rejected
Physical Performance	0.067	0.062	0.084	1.087	0.001	Ho is rejected
Psychological Outlook	0.116	0.062	0.145	1.861	0.278	Fail to reject Ho
Social Interaction	0.078	0.046	0.103	1.700	0.064	Fail to reject Ho
Preventive Health	0.106	0.046	0.131	2.311	0.090	Fail to reject Ho
Dependent Variable: Academic Productivity						
*p<0.05	R=0.651	adjusted R ² =0.416	F=54.910	p-value=0.000		

The regression analysis revealed that only life enhancement and physical performance are significant variables. This means that these two specific variables have a statistically significant impact on the outcome being studied, while the other variables in the model are not statistically significant. The significant results of the t-test indicate that the estimated regression coefficients for life enhancement and physical performance are significantly different from zero. This suggests that only these two variables, and not the other variables, are meaningful additions to the model in explaining the observed levels of academic productivity among the respondents. A significant portion of the differences or changes in academic productivity levels among the respondents can be explained by the influence of physical exercise-related factors, specifically life enhancement and physical performance. These variables play a key role in accounting for the variation in academic productivity levels observed in the study.

Regression Analysis on How the Domains of Socio-emotional Skills predict Academic Productivity

Using Multiple Linear Regression analysis, the regression model of academic productivity in terms of the domains of socio-emotional skills is:

$$Y = 0.953 + 0.120X_1 + 0.058X_2 + 0.261X_3 + 0.084X_4 + 0.181X_5$$

The results of the Student's t-test, shown above indicate that only self-awareness, self-management, and responsible decision making are significant. These results prove that the estimated regression coefficients of said indicators are significantly different from zero, signifying only self-awareness, self-management, and responsible decision making are meaningful additions to the model. Consequently, F-test revealed that the composite hypothesis that all regression coefficients are equal to zero is also highly significant with an F-statistic of 89.835 and a p-value of < 0.000. Finally, the adjusted R² revealed that the model could explain approximately 54% of the variation in the level of academic productivity of the students. This suggests that 54% of the variability in the observed levels of academic productivity of the respondents can be attributed to the domains of socio-emotional skills.

Table 7. Regression Analysis on How the Domains of Socio-emotional Skills predict Academic Productivity

Model	Unstandardized coefficients	t-value	p-value	Decision
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PRODUCTIVITY AMONG COLLEGE STUDENTS**

	B	Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients Beta			
(Constant)	0.953	0.137		6.963	0.000	
Self-awareness	0.120	0.056	0.143	2.152	0.032	Ho is rejected
Social Awareness	0.058	0.045	0.073	1.298	0.195	Fail to reject Ho
Self-management	0.261	0.039	0.325	6.635	0.000	Ho is rejected
Relationship Management	0.084	0.049	0.102	1.709	0.088	Fail to reject Ho
Responsible Decision Making	0.181	0.051	0.216	3.525	0.000	Ho is rejected
Dependent Variable: Academic Productivity						
*p<0.05	R=0.739	adjusted R ² =0.540		F=89.835	p-value=0.000	

The results of the regression analysis discovered that only self-awareness, self-management, and responsible decision-making are statistically significant variables in the model being studied. This means that these three specific variables have a significant impact on the outcome, while the other variables included in the analysis are not statistically significant. The significant results of the t-test suggest that the estimated regression coefficients for self-awareness, self-management, and responsible decision-making are significantly different from zero. This indicates that only these three variables contribute meaningfully to the model and play important roles in explaining the observed levels of academic productivity among the respondents. A substantial portion of the differences or variations in academic productivity levels among the respondents can be explained by the influence of socio-emotional factors, specifically self-awareness, self-management, and responsible decision-making. These variables are key contributors to the variability in academic productivity levels observed in the study.

Regression Analysis on Physical Exercise and Socio-emotional Skills predict Academic Productivity

Using Multiple Linear Regression analysis, the regression model of academic productivity in terms of physical exercise and socio-emotional skills is:

$$Y = 0.869 + 0.164X_1 + 0.559X_2$$

Table 8. Regression Analysis Physical Exercise and Socio-emotional Skills predict Academic Productivity

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**PHYSICAL EXERCISE AND SOCIO-EMOTIONAL SKILLS AS PREDICTORS TO ACADEMIC
PRODUCTIVITY AMONG COLLEGE STUDENTS**

Model	Unstandardized coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t-value	p-value	Decision
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
(Constant)	0.869	0.141		6.168	0.000	
Physical Exercise	0.164	0.053	0.178	3.060	0.002	Ho is rejected
Socio-emotional skills	0.559	0.055	0.586	10.091	0.000	Ho is rejected
Dependent Variable: Academic Productivity						
*p<0.05	R=0.736	adjusted R ² =0.539		F=222.877	p-value=0.000	

The results of the Student's t-test, shown above indicate that all variables are significant. These results prove that the estimated regression coefficients of said indicators are significantly different from zero, signifying that both Physical Exercise and socio-emotional skills are meaningful additions to the model. Consequently, F-test revealed that the composite hypothesis that all regression coefficients are equal to zero is also highly significant with an F-statistic of 222.877 and a p-value of < 0.000. Finally, the adjusted R² revealed that the model could explain approximately 54% of the variation in the level of academic productivity of the students. This suggests that 54% of the variability in the observed levels of academic productivity of the respondents can be attributed to Physical Exercise and socio-emotional skills.

The results regression analysis has shown that all variables included in the analysis are significant. This means that each variable has a statistically significant impact on the outcome being studied. The significant results of the t-test indicate that the estimated regression coefficients for these variables are significantly different from zero. Specifically, the analysis indicates that both Physical Exercise and socio-emotional skills play meaningful roles in the model being examined. This suggests that these variables are important predictors of the observed levels of academic productivity among the respondents. There are more than half of the changes or differences in academic productivity levels can be explained by the influence of these two variables in the model. In other words, Physical Exercise and socio-emotional skills are significant factors that account for a substantial portion of the variation in academic productivity among the respondents

5. Recommendations

After a profound consideration of the possible implications of the findings and conclusion of the study, the researcher came up with several recommendations on how students can improve their academic productivity. First, to escalate the level of physical exercise to very high, the college instructors shall include "Brain Breaks" in the teaching and learning process. Especially physical exercise is one of the indicators of physical exercise that significantly impacts academic productivity among college students; movement-based activities like Brain Breaks shall be employed in the instruction. These simple physical and mental exercises will allow the students to refocus, relax and breathe. It will also help them improve their performance in doing the tasks at hand.

Secondly, to improve the level of life enhancement to very high, the institution shall strengthen its implementation of the Health and Wellness Program, especially since it was discovered to have a significant impact on academic productivity. This program is not limited to providing physical activities to its stakeholders but also conducts seminars about its effects on their lives. Students' engagement in the said program should be strictly monitored. Additionally, self-awareness, self-management, and responsible decision-making are proven to have significant meaning to academic productivity.

To significantly enhance its educational standards, the institution will offer workshops and seminars focused on the Social and Emotional Learning (SEL) Framework. This initiative is designed to equip students with essential self-management skills, fostering their ability to regulate their emotions, set and achieve goals, and handle stress effectively. Additionally, the program will work to develop students' self-awareness, helping them to understand their strengths and areas for growth. By advancing students' abilities to make caring and constructive choices, the initiative aims to prepare them to navigate a variety of social and academic situations with confidence. Integrating these key components of the SEL Framework into the curriculum will ensure that students receive a comprehensive education that supports their emotional and social development alongside their academic achievements.

The "Together at School Program" aims to enhance the student consultation process by introducing formalized guidelines for tracking academic involvement and performance. This initiative seeks to provide a structured framework that allows educators to closely monitor students' progress and address any issues they may encounter. By implementing these guidelines, the program intends to streamline the process of identifying and resolving learning blocks and concerns, ensuring that students receive timely support. Additionally, the program will facilitate more efficient communication between students and educational staff, helping to accelerate the resolution of academic challenges. Ultimately, the "Together at School Program" is designed to foster a more supportive and responsive learning environment, promoting better academic outcomes and overall student success.

6. Conclusion

Referring back to the result of the research objective, the researcher has concluded that physical exercise in terms of life enhancement, physical performance, psychological outlook, social interaction, and preventive health influence the academic productivity among college students. Furthermore, student motivation in terms of self-awareness, social awareness, self-management, relationship management, and responsible decision making also influence college students' academic productivity.

The findings revealed that physical exercise in terms of Preventive Health, Physical Performance, Life Enhancement, and Psychological Outlook is much observed by college students. Among the indicators of physical exercise, social interaction is moderately observed by the college students. On the other hand, the level of student motivation in terms of Self-awareness, Responsible Decision Making, Relationship Management, Social Awareness, Self-management, is much observed by college students. Overall, the results revealed that there is a significant relationship between all domains in physical exercise and socio-emotional skills have significant relationship to academic productivity.

The results of the student's t-test in the variable, physical exercise indicate that only life enhancement and physical performance are significant. The results proved that the estimated regression coefficients of said indicators are significantly different from zero, signifying only life enhancement and physical performance are meaningful additions to the model. While the results of the student's t-test in the variable socio-emotional skills indicate that only self-awareness, self-management, and responsible decision making are significant. These results prove that the estimated regression coefficients of said indicators are significantly different from zero, signifying only self-awareness, self-management, and responsible decision making are meaningful additions to the model.

When taken as one, the results of the student's t-test, shown above indicate that all variables are significant. These results prove that the estimated regression coefficients of said indicators are significantly different from zero, signifying that both Physical Exercise and socio-emotional skills are meaningful additions to the model.

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8. About the Author(s)

Jeric E. Suguis is a seasoned professional in the field of sports education and management. With extensive experience as a physical education instructor and currently serving as the Sports, Culture, and Arts Development Unit Head at Davao de Oro State College, he holds an Instructor III position. His commitment to the field extends to his roles as a Board Member of the National Organization of Physical Education and Sports and as Business Officer of the Physical Education Association of Mindanao. Mr. Suguis has a strong research focus, encompassing physical education, sports science, sports performance, and athletic preparation. His significant contributions to the field are reflected in his published articles in reputable journals, which highlight his expertise and dedication to advancing sports and physical education.

Conflict of Interest Statement

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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